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USING TECHNOLOGY ASSESSMENT IN TECHNICAL STUDY PROGRAMS AS A MEANS TO FOSTER ETHICAL REFLECTIONS ON THE SOCIETAL EFFECTS OF TECHNOLOGIES AND ENGINEERING SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

To disseminate knowledge of Technology Assessment (TA) to the engineering ethics education research community this paper provides an overview of existing TA models: consequentialist TA, interdisciplinary TA, ethical TA, hermeneutical TA, participatory TA, and constructivist TA. The central result of the presented work is an analysis of how the different TA models compare to the science – society interface, including how the models relate to ethics, roles of experts, participation of stakeholders and the public, and output formats. It briefly mentions how the models are introduced in classes and used by students at Aalborg University in the 2nd semester of the bachelor program in Techno-Anthropology. Feedback from students indicate that they request concrete instructions on how to apply the models in their project work. All this to provide an argument for initiating research in how TA can be taught in Technical Study Programs as a means to foster ethical reflections on the societal effects of technologies and engineering solutions.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Technology Assessment (TA) is a collection of approaches focused on evaluating the short- and long-term consequences of the technologies under assessment. A technology assessment can focus on technological consequences for the economy, public health, the environment, democracy, culture, the good life, sustainability etc. There exists a number of TA models, and in this concept paper I describe and compare some of them. The rationale for doing this is that TA can be used in engineering ethics education as a means to stimulate ethical reflections on the wider consequences of technological solutions, which is a central skill for future engineers [1, 2]. To validate this claim a lot is needed. One thing that is needed is a good understanding of different TA models and how they compare. I will in this paper provide such an overview, and discuss very first ideas on application in education. Hence, I endeavour to promote a good understanding of different TA-models within the engineering ethics education research community.

TA is located between engineering science and politics / society as it is often, but not always, set up to support political decisions regarding public investment in technological solutions or legislation framing technological issues. Decision-makers are, as mentioned above, not always the target group of the TA. Sometimes the target group of a TA is engineers and technology designers when the idea is to implement ethical values or stakeholder perspectives in technological design [3, 4]

There are additional central tensions between the presented TA tools. Should TA experts only provide relevant information on the wider implications of technologies to facilitate politicians and decision-makers' decisions regarding technologies? Or, are they themselves expected to make assessments and estimates? Put in another way, how normative is TA supposed to be? [5].

A related tension regards who should do the TAs: Experts, scientific institutions, public authorities, or representatives of the public? And in this connection one can enquire the role of the engineers who are involved in TA. Roger Pielke Jr [6] distinguishes between five different roles of experts supporting politicians and decision-makers:

- Pure scientists (whose role are limited to summarizing the state of knowledge in a particular field),
- Science arbiters (who provide detailed answers to policymakers' specific questions),
- Issue advocates (who offer their expertise as resources in political battle)
- Stealth issue advocates (who disguise themselves as pure scientists, but are really advocating an issue) and
- Honest brokers (who clarify existing policy options and identify new ones).

In this concept paper, I present six TA models: Consequential technology assessment, Interdisciplinary technology assessment, Ethical technology assessment, Hermeneutical technology assessment, Participatory technology assessment and Constructivist technology assessment.

I will also compare these models with regard to the whether the models are purely descriptive, who is supposed to do the assessment, and the role of the engineers involved in the technology assessment.

2 TECHNOLOGY ASSESSMENT MODELS

2.1 Classical Technology assessment

What I call the classical TA model is the model used by the Office of Technology Assessment (OTA) [7]. OTA was set up in Washington DC, USA in 1974. Its role was to support the congress in its assessment of presidential proposals to invest in new technologies. Until 1974, the congress had acted as a rubber stamp as its members rarely had a technical background, and hence found it difficult to assess the technology proposals coming from the president's office. A central objective was to gain control over the negative implications of technology for human health and the environment. However, a focus on the financial implications also quickly became important in OTA's assessments.

In 1995 OTA closed down. The argument put forward by republicans underpinning this decision, was that it was expensive to have a special institution for technology assessment. Money could be saved, if technology assessment tasks were solved by other institutions.

The Federation of American Scientists hosts a digital repository of all technology assessment performed by OTA. OTA's technology assessment model was consequentialist in the sense that it almost in a positivistic sense tried to predict the wider consequences of technologies under assessment. This is rarely possible, and maybe this positivistic approach to knowledge about the future made the office fall out of synch with the post-modern waves in the 1990s?

The technology assessment experts were only supposed to present 'objective knowledge' of the wider impacts of technologies under assessment. The power over the TAs were situated in a congressional subcommittee with political majority over experts. It would decide which technologies OTA would assess and draw political conclusions from OTA's work. In terms of Pielke's topology, OTA's technology assessment model reflects the role of the science arbiter.

2.2 Interdisciplinary technology assessment

Armin Grunwald is the 'guru' of technology assessment. To revitalize TA after OTA was closed down he presented in the late 1990s and the beginning of 2000s a revised TA model [5]. Grunwald states that the background for the emergence of this TA model is the ambivalence of technology. There is a need for an early warning mechanism in relation to technological risk. Risks are often invisible, and require a scientific lens to identify. There is a need to involve experts, who in the

interdisciplinary TA model also should have a strong normative flavor and recommend political decisions.

Hence, Grunwald suggests to merge technology ethics and classical technology assessment. The interdisciplinary technology assessment model involves representatives from different disciplines. It focuses on producing knowledge and information. This classic trait of technology assessment is then merged with ethical reasoning to guide the making of assessments and decisions. Ethical assessment / decision-making and classical technology assessment form a hybrid here.

In this model the TA experts both do both the science and policy recommendations. Grunwald's early technology assessment model only to some extent abandoned the consequentialist flavor of classical technology assessment, it is experts from different disciplines that do the assessment, though it adds normative and epistemological reflections to TA. In terms of Pielke's expert roles, it can be labelled 'pure science', as Grunwald delegate freedom to make recommendations to interdisciplinary assessment teams, and possibly 'science advocates' if they draw strong ethical or political conclusions from the expected technological effects.

2.3 Ethical technology assessment

A variant of interdisciplinary technology assessment that emphasizes and puts special focus on ethical judgment following the assessment of future consequences of a technology is often denoted Ethical technology assessment. Palm and Hansson makes the argument that there is a deficit of ethics in most TA models in the sense that little attention is made on how exactly to draw ethical conclusions based on an assessment of expected implications [8]. To remedy this lack of ethical reflection in technology assessment they proposed a list of ethical assessment criteria that can guide an ethical assessment:

1. "Dissemination and use of information
2. Control, influence and power
3. Impact on social contact patterns
4. Privacy
5. Sustainability
6. Human reproduction
7. Gender, minorities and justice
8. International relations
9. Impact on human values." [8].

I have made a list of 20 ethical assessment criteria that an ethical technology analysis can be based on [9]. I also suggest that ethical technology assessments should not only focus on the intended consequences, but also address possible abuse, long and short-term side effects and societal as well as cultural implications.

The target group of ethical technology assessment is engineers and technical experts in the sense that it does not aim at legislation, but rather in responsible innovation and ethical design.

Ethical technology assessment overlaps with many of the traits of interdisciplinary technology assessment, though it clarifies the normative dimension of interdisciplinary technology assessment and provides an argument for undertaking the role of the ‘issue advocate’ in specific situations.

2.4 Hermeneutic technology assessment

In later years Grunwald [10, 11] has developed a second approach to TA, the so-called hermeneutic technology assessment model. You can use this TA model when there is no valid knowledge, predictions or scenarios available about a technology's implications and consequences.

Hence, it is a criticism of or an alternative to consequentialist TA models that can easily shut down future opportunities on a false basis. Hermeneutic technology assessment considers knowledge about the future uncertain.

What this approach assesses is techno-visionary futures or future narratives, visions, expectations, and notions of new or future technologies. It is about technologies that do not exist or have not yet been implemented. It is about finding the meaning of ideas about new and emerging technologies. Hermeneutic technology assessment is anticipatory.

This model interprets texts, diagrams, oral presentations and works of art regarding imagined future technologies. The sender of techno-imaginaries can be science fiction writers and other artists, companies, organizations, politicians, scientific academies, futurists, intellectuals or entrepreneurs.

The assessment starts by choosing an iconoclastic intervention in the public debate regarding a non-existing, emerging or new technology. The intervention is interpreted in terms of what it says about its present context, how it has influenced the public debate, which reactions it caused and what we can learn from the resulting debates. A hermeneutic technology assessment is itself an intervention into the debate, and can itself be the starting point of a hermeneutic technology assessment.

This model has a focus on advising politicians and decision makers. The technical designers and technology developers are not the target audience. This approach to TA comes closest to the role of ‘the honest broker’.

2.5 Participatory technology assessment Tables

The Danish Board of Technology (DBT), among others, have developed models for technology assessment where citizens do the assessment.² These models have names like Consensus conference, Citizens' jury, Citizens' summit, and Kitchen table meeting. The idea is that a dilemma regarding a technology is identified – typically two arguments *pro et contra* regarding the implementation of a technology in a specific context – and that this dilemma is presented to a representative group of citizens. The size of the group depend on the chosen model, and can vary from several hundred people down to a number of meetings each attended by a handful of friends. The dilemma is presented to the citizens by experts or in material prepared by TA experts.

All these models share an underpinning assumption, here captured by Andreas Birkbak, Anders Koed Madsen and Anders Kristian Munk of the TANTlab at AAU:

“They are rooted in expert evaluations about potential consequences and possibilities of a given technology - not in the free-running imagination of a lay person. Second, organising deliberation across tables around cross-cutting dilemmas eases the communication of ‘public opinion’. Because the citizens are discussing comparable issues, they appear as a uniform public that - despite disagreeing on solutions - share each other's framings of the problems. In sum, the DBT approach to TA stages citizen involvement as a moderated endeavour that sits between expert-driven problem formulations and the output of findings to pass on to decision-makers.” [12].

In participatory technology assessment there is a distribution of labor in the sense that experts feed into to a dilemma associated with a technology, citizen do the assessment, and decision-makers receive the citizens' recommendations as input to policy-making.

The role of the joined set of disagreeing technical experts and facilitating TA experts is to act as ‘honest brokers’ in the sense that different opportunities are presented that the citizens can choose between.

The proceedings from last years' SEFI conference include a paper that combines participatory and ethical technology assessment [13]. In the presented hybrid approach participants in a workshop both feed into the factual discussions on the implications of the assessed technology and do a collective ethical assessment.

2.6 Constructivist technology assessment

The script underpinning Constructive technology assessment is to replace an existing technology with a new technology [14]. It asks ‘What can the existing

² More information about the DBT and its technology assessment models are found at their website: <https://tekno.dk/?lang=en> [accessed May, 5 2021].

technology that the new technology must also be able to do?’ and ‘What should the new technology add?’ There are two movements 1) an historical analysis (a la SCOT) where one looks back at what choices were made, and which stakeholders negotiated when the technology was established. And, 2) a move where selected stakeholders look forward and collectively try to shape the new technology that will replace the existing one.

Constructive technology assessment perceives technology as a process (not a thing). It consists of four assessment criteria elements: What is the purpose of the technology? Is the organization synchronized for adopting the technology? Do employees have the needed knowledge to operate the technology? And do the technical elements work according to the purpose, the organization and the human landscape?

Another central assumption in this approach to TA is that affected stakeholders should be included in TA [14]. TA is not only (but also) for experts and engineers. Universities, civil society, public authorities and businesses are often mentioned as stakeholders that all must be included in TA.

Hence, TA is not a business for experts and engineers only. All the stakeholders in the technology assessment will act as issue advocates in the sense that they will bend the technology and the assessment in their direction. This is a means towards social acceptance. The TA experts will facilitate this negotiation, and act as honest brokers.

2.7 Comparison

To compare the different TA models I have set up a matrix where the different TA models are listed in the rows of the matrix. In the columns different items are listed that the TA models relate to in different ways: Who is the target group of the technology assessment model?, Who should be involved in the technology assessment process?, What is the role of the TA experts?, Should the TA experts conduct an ethical judgment?

The resulting comparison are seen in Figure 1:

	Target group	Who is involved?	Role of TA experts	Judgment by TA experts?
<i>Classic TA</i>	Politicians	Engineers, politicians	Science arbiter	No
<i>Interdisciplinary TA</i>	Politicians	Engineers, other experts	Pure scientist and possibly issue advocate	Yes
<i>Ethical TA</i>	Tech designers	Engineers, ethicists	Issue advocate	Yes

<i>Hermeneutical TA</i>	Public debate	Humanists	Honest broker	Yes
<i>Participatory TA</i>	Politicians	Engineers, other experts, citizens	Honest broker	No
<i>Constructivist TA</i>	Tech designers	Academia, public authorities, business, civil society	Honest broker	Yes. Joint judgement by all stakeholders

Figure 1 shows the field of technology assessment with some of its different models. We see that the different technology assessment models are quite different when it comes to target group, involvement of different groups, and the role of the technology assessment expert.

3 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION RESULTS

3.1 Tables

I have used the above described topology to present the field of technology assessment to Techno-Anthropology bachelor students at the 2nd semester in the spring of 2021. I presented each model in lectures followed by group discussions. The presentation of the TA models were part of a city engineering and planning course of formal reasons, and ran over six teaching sessions. The presentation of the field of TA was otherwise not linked to city engineering and planning. It could have also have been located as part of an engineering ethics course or in a separate course headlined ‘Technology assessment’.

As all bachelor programs at Aalborg University Techno-Anthropology follows the principles of Problem-based learning. Each semester is split up in course modules (half of the time – 15 ETCS) and project modules (the remaining half – 15 ECTS). In the students’ project work on the 2nd semester they are required to apply one of the TA models on a technology relevant to use by a municipality. Most student groups ended up assessing use of digital tools in social work. Few students assessed block chain technology to share info among municipalities or technologies to promote public health or foster green transition. By the time of writing this paper the students have not yet handed in their reports, but they have chosen which technology assessment model they apply: Around half of the student groups are using ethical technology assessment (6 groups), the remaining groups are divided between participatory (1 group), constructivist (3 groups) and hermeneutical technology assessment (1 group).

The topology did induce reflections among the project groups, as they needed to link their project to one of the models. It both helped the students to clarify their project and provided an overview of the field of TA.

Feedback from students at a midterm evaluation meeting indicated that they request concrete instructions on how to apply the models in their project work. Otherwise, the students found it difficult to do so. Hence, I provided clear instructions on the different steps of all the models except classic technology assessment.

Next time I offer this overview of TA models to students on the 2nd semester of Techno-Anthropology, I will revise the tasks I embed in the teaching. This year they were directed towards understanding and comparing the different technology models. I have previously had success in my teaching with embedding student presentations on pre-defined case studies [15, 16]. I will include case oriented tasks asking students to present concrete technology assessments that follow the instructions of the different models.

Many questions can be asked to whether TA is an useful approach to stimulate ethical reflections among engineering and technical science students. Hence, more research is needed to define and answer those. However, before these questions can be addressed an understanding of different TA-models must be conveyed to the engineering ethics education research community. This concept paper has tried to do just that.

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